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The epidemiology of war-like injuries in children and adolescents during postwar violence wave: Experience of a teaching hospital in Baghdad.

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Abstract

Background: In most developing countries communicable diseases continue to be a major cause of childhood morbidity and mortality. However in this geographic area of the world war-like injury involving civilians including children has become a massive health problem. These injuries produce a significant burden on medical facilities. The human and economic costs of the injuries are tremendous.

Objective: The aim of this study is to report the occurrence of war-like injuries in children and adolescents during postwar violence wave

Materials and Method: The pattern of war-like injuries in 272 injured children and adolescents aged 15 years or less admitted to the casualty unit at the University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia (UHK) over a 2 year period from March 2003 to March 2005 was studied. These injuries occurred during the post-war violence wave. **Results:** The injuries in the majority of casualties were caused by explosions in civilian areas, mortar bombardment of civilian's buildings and housing and family assassinations.

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The injuries were more common in males with a male to female ratio of (3.1/1), 206 (75.7%) of the casualties were males and 66 (24.3%) were females. Of the 272 casualties studied, 52 (19.1%) were 5 years old or less, 95 (34.9%) were between 6 to 11 years, and 125 (45.9%) were between 12 to 15 years. There were 126 (46.3%) minor casualties, which were managed in the outpatient emergency unit, while 146 (53.6%) casualties had serious and major injuries, 120 (44.1%) of whom were admitted to (UHK) and 6 were transferred to other hospitals. 20 (7%) casualties died (12 on arrival and 9 during resuscitation) and two casualties were discharged by parent shortly after receiving them without adequate medical evaluation. Fragmentation weapons (blast injuries) caused 216 (79.4%) casualties and 54 (19.8%) casualties sustained gunshot wounds and 2 (0.7%) substantiated burn. Injuries to the lower limbs and trunk were the most common injuries in this series accounting for 126 (46.3%) of all injuries.

Conclusion: Recognition of the potential for pediatric casualties in the violence wave in this geographic area is

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necessary to facilitate appropriate planning, training and equipping of casualty units.

Introduction

In most developing countries communicable diseases continue to be a major cause of childhood morbidity and mortality. However in Iraq, war- injuries involving civilians including children has become a massive health problem. These injuries produce a significant burden on medical facilities. The human and economic costs of the injuries are tremendous.

Exposure of children and adolescents to injuries during war time has been increasingly reported in this geographic area [1, 2]. During the first two weeks of the 2003 gulf conflict, the sole British field hospital in the region received 482 casualties, eight of which (1.7%) were children. During the same conflict, the 202 Field Hospital reported that the first child casualty arrived two days later and over the next four weeks there were 24 admissions of patients aged 15 years or less, amounting to 2% of the total admissions. Although exposure of children and adolescents to injuries during war time has been increasingly reported in this geographic area, an epidemic of war-related wounds during postwar violence in children and adolescence has not been reported in the medical literature. The aim of this study is to report the occurrence of war-like injuries in children and adolescents during two years of post-war violence wave.

Materials and Methods

The pattern of war-related injuries in 272 injured children and adolescents

admitted to the casualty unit at the University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia (UHK) over a 2 years period March 2003 to March 2005 was studied. All data on war- related injuries in children and adolescents 15 years of age or younger were collected .These injuries occurred during post war violence wave. The precise numbers of the total admissions to the casualty unit were not available to the investigators because of the poor recording system during this period of crisis. The precise numbers of the total admissions to the casualty unit were not available to the investigators because of the less serious cases tend to be discharged without being recorded or registered.

Results

The injuries in the majority of casualties were caused by explosions in civilian areas, mortar bombardment of civilian's buildings and housing and family assassinations. There were more males 206 (75.7%) than females 66 (24.3 %) among the casualties with a male to female ratio of (3.1/1). Those who were 5 years of age or less comprised 52 (19.1%) of the casualties, while 95 (34.9%) were between 6 - 11 years, and 125 (45.9%) were between 12 - 15 years.

Figure (1) shows the age distribution of the casualties.

Of the 272 casualties received, 126 (46.3%) were considered minor and were managed in the outpatient emergency unit without hospitalization. Two casualties were discharged on the responsibility of their parents shortly after receiving them without adequate medical evaluation to assess the seriousness of their injury., while 146(53.3%) casualties had serious and major injuries; 120 (44.1%) of whom were admitted to (UHK), and 6 transferred to other hospitals. 20 casualties (7%) died (12 on arrival and 9 during resuscitation).

The injuries were generally classified as blast injuries with shells from fragmentation weapons and gunshot injuries with bullets. 216(79.4%) casualties suffered wounds from fragmentation weapons (blast injuries) and 54 (19.8%) casualties sustained gunshot wounds (Bullet injuries) and 2 (0.8%) burns.

According to the anatomical location and extent of injury, the injuries fell into

6 categories Table (1). Injuries to the lower limbs and trunk were the most common injuries in this series account for 42% of all injuries. Of the 120 casualties admitted to this hospital 35 were admitted to the general surgery and wards and 30 to the neurosurgery wards. The remaining cases were admitted to other surgical wards, as shown in Table (2).

Discussion

Exposure of children and adolescents to injuries during war time has been increasingly reported in this geographic area [1, 2]. During the first two weeks of the 2003 gulf conflict, the sole British field hospital in the region received 482 casualties, eight of which (1.7%) were children. During the same conflict, the 202 Field Hospital reported that the first child casualty arrived two days later and over the next four weeks there were 24 admissions of patients aged 15 years or less, amounting to 2% of the total admissions [3].

Type of injury according to the anatomical location & extent	Blast injuries, (Shells from fragmentation weapons) Number (%)	Gunshot wounds (Bullet injuries) Number (%)	burn	Total Casualties Number (%)
Head & Neck	47 (17.2%)	13 (4.8%)		60 (22%)
Upper limb & Shoulder	40 (14.7%)	3 (1.1%)		43 (15.8%)
Trunk	29 (10.6%)	17 (6.5%)		46 (17.1%)
- Thoracic	11 (4.3%)	5 (1.5%)		16 (5.8%)
- Abdomen and back	16(5.6%)	11 (4.3%)		27 (9.9%)
- pelvis	2 (0.7%)	1 (0.4%)		3 (1.1%)
Lower Limb	61 (22.8%)	19 (6.5%)		80 (29.4%)
Reached dead	8(3%)	2(0.7%)	2(0.7%)	12(4.4%)
Generalized	31(11.3%)	0		31(11.3%)
Total (%)	216(79.4%)	54(19.8%)	2(0.8%)	272(100%)

*One or more injuries per case

Table (1): Categories of injuries according to the anatomical location and extent of injury

Hospital Wards	Admitted Causalities
General surgery	35(12.8%)
Neurosurgery	30(11%)
Cardiothoracic surgery	24(8%)
Orthopedic surgery	21(7.7%)
Facio-maxillary surgery	4(1.4%)
Intensive care unit	2(0.7%)
Ophthalmology / Urology / Plastic surgery	4(1.4%)
Total (100%)	120(44.1%)

Table (2): Table (2): Distribution of the hospitalized patient to various hospital departments

The Pattern of injuries in the present study was different from the pattern of injuries to children and adolescents during war time like that reported by Gurney [3]. from which country and in which war. In that retrospective analysis of Seventy eight children (All <16-years-old) admitted to a British Army Field Hospital during war fighting, 44 (56%) children had burns as the principal injury; 7 (9%) had shrapnel injuries, 5 (6%) had blunt trauma from a road traffic accident (this is not war-related). Only one child had Gun-shot wounds. 'Medical' complaints rather than trauma accounted for 17% of attendances and 78% of

children required transfer to a specialist facility.

The present paper is a unique one reporting an epidemic of war-related injuries among children and adolescents during the post-war wave of violence in Iraq that has not been reported in the medical literature.

Conclusion: Recognition of the potential for pediatric casualties during the violence wave in Iraq is necessary to facilitate appropriate planning, training and equipping of causality units.

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